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Evaluating The Performance Of Huber And Bisquare Weighting Functions On Some Robust Estimators: An Empirical Approach

Abdullahi Yusuf Jibrin^{1*}, Ahmed Abdulkadir², Mohammed Salawu Atureta³, Abdulmalik Mohammed⁴ & Musa Usman Bawa⁵

^{1,2,3&5} Department of Statistics,
Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Computer/Mathematics Education,
College of Education Dutsen Tanshi Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: Abdullahi Yusuf Jibrin, Email: yuzarseef406@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to evaluate the performance of Huber and Bisquare weights on M and MM robust estimators in the presence of outliers in robust regression model using a default and adjusted tuning constant values, so as to see the impact of increasing or reducing the tuning constant values on the resistibility of the robust estimators. The study used a real data for the evaluation of Huber and Bisquare weights on the analysis of effects of electricity consumption on the economic growth of Nigeria from 1989-2022. The result of the study showed that increasing or decreasing the tuning constant values for M estimators have a significant impact on the resistibility of the estimators. while adjusting the tuning constant value for MM-estimator has no impact on the robust regression. The result of the study shows that over time higher electricity consumption can give rise to more economic growth just as economic growth may stimulate increased consumption of electricity in the long run. The study also recommends that analyst should use smaller value than the default turning constant for M-estimation to have more resistibility against outlying observations in the regression models, because the smaller the tuning constant value the more resistant the M-estimator. Likewise, the study recommends that government should formulate appropriate policy mix that would motivate the firms in the electricity industry to enhance improved performance and contribution of the sector.

Keywords: Outlier, Tuning Constant, M-estimation, MM-estimation, Electricity consumption, Economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

A robust regression is an iterative procedure that is designed to overcome the problem of outliers and influential observations in the data and minimize their impact over the regression coefficients. Robust regression analysis provides an alternative to a least squares regression model when fundamental assumptions are unfulfilled by nature of the data. Sometimes, the analyst can transform his variables to

agree to those assumptions. However, a transformation will not eliminate the leverage of influential outliers that bias the prediction and distort the significance of parameter estimates (David *et al.*, 2017). Under these circumstances, robust regression that is resistant to the influence of outliers may be a potential recourse.

The method of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is the most frequently applied regression Technique. The application of this specific method requires several assumptions. Every researcher is aware of the fact that the OLS method performs poorly if these assumptions are not fulfilled. But in particular outlying observation observations within the data can cause violations of model assumptions and thereby can have huge impact on regression results (Begashaw and Yohannes (2020)). Estimating parameters with OLS must fulfill some prescribed assumptions, with errors mutually independent and normal with a middle value and variance (Fernandes et al, 2014).

According to Abonazel and Rabie, (2019) when the data set is contaminated with a single or few outliers, the problem of identifying such observations becomes serious problem. We note that in most cases, data sets contain more outliers or a group of influential observations. Two types of outliers can happen in the regression dataset. One with extremely large values in the response is referred to as vertical outliers, whereas observations with extremely large values in the explanatory variable are called leverage points. Outliers being influential to the classical regression require methods that are insensitive to it (Khan *et al.*, 2021). Outliers and high leverage points often exert too much influence and consequently become responsible for misleading conclusion about the fitting of a regression model, causing multicollinearity problems, masking and/or swamping of outliers etc (Abu Sayed *et al.*, 2020).

A common method of robust regression is the M estimate, introduced by Huber (1964), which is as efficient as Ordinary Least Square (OLS), and is considered the simplest approach. The Least Trimmed Squares (LTS) estimation was introduced by Rousseeuw (1984), and is a high breakdown value method. So, too, is the S estimation, another high breakdown value method with a higher statistical efficiency than LTS estimation (Rousseeuw & Yohai, 1984). The S estimation is used to minimize the dispersion of residuals. The MM estimation, a special type of M-estimation introduced by Yohai (1987), combines high breakdown value estimation and efficient estimation. The M estimation has a higher breakdown value and greater statistical efficiency than the S estimation. The well-known methods of robust estimation are M-estimation, S- estimation and MM-estimation.

In statistics, the Huber loss is a loss function used in robust regression, that is less sensitive to outliers in data than the squared error loss. Huber is useful as a loss function in robust statistics or machine learning to reduce the influence of outliers as compared to the common squared error loss, residuals with a magnitude higher than δ are not squared Weighted regression can be used to correct for heteroscedasticity. In a Weighted regression procedure, more weight is given to the observations with smaller variance because these observations provide more reliable information about the regression function than those with large variances.

Electricity Consumption in Nigeria

Electricity power or energy is the bedrock for economic growth and industrialization of Nigeria. The process of setting up of an electricity generating system is costly and time consuming but once it is in place, it is expected to experience a decreasing average costs as the output expands. Also, the system is expected to innovate and make use of advances in knowledge and technology. These learning and experiences so far gained on the production process should enable the system expand and produce better output than previously as a result of the existence of the economy of scale as well as the learning effects. Nigeria has never enjoyed an adequate supply of electricity in its history as unmet demand and constant losses have been the characteristics of electricity generation. Prior to Nigeria's independence, electricity was known and used only by some government headquarters and the first electricity plant was built in 1950 and government corporate a department to form the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN) with the sole responsibility for generation, distribution, transmission and sale of electricity to all consumers in the country. After independence in 1960, the Niger Dam Authority (NDA) was promulgated in 1962 by an Act of parliament with similar functions as the ECN and it operated the electricity industry from 1962 –1972. To make the industry efficient, the two agencies (ECN and NDA) were merged and transformed to the Nigerian Electric

Power Authority (NEPA) in 1973 as a limited liability company. It acquired Ijora, Delta, Afam and Kainji power stations with a total installed capacity of 532.6MW serving more than two million Nigerians. Salisu *et al.*, (2023), Investigated the performance of Some robust estimators using Huber Weights in the presence of outliers and high leverage points in the presence of outliers in regression model, using a default and adjusted turning constant values of the Huber weights, so as to see the impact of increasing/reducing the tuning constant values on the resistibility of the robust estimators. But the redecent weights investigated by the previous researchers is not much insensitive to the effect of large outliers. Therefore, this study intends to Improve on their work by examining the behavior of another redecent weight called Bisquare which is more resistant to the effect of outliers by adjusting the default values of the tuning constant, so as to see the impact of increasing or reducing the tuning constant values on the resistibility of some robust estimators for the analysis of electricity consumption on the economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the literature reviewed, it was found that all the previous researchers applied the non-robust estimators for determining the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate the impact / effect of increasing / decreasing the default turning constant values on M and MM estimators for both Huber and Bisquare for the analysis of electricity consumption on the economic growth of Nigeria. The study used a time series data ranges from 1989 – 2022, the variables on which data were collected include Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which has been used as a proxy to economic growth and depended variable while Electricity Supply (ESS), Gross capital formation (GCF) and Total labour forces (TLF) are the independent variables that will empirically analyse the impact of electricity consumption on economic growth in Nigeria. The study would help analyst/researchers to know which method will produce the best estimate when there is change in value in both direction (increase or decrease). Since outliers and high leverage point often causes a huge explanatory mishap in regression modeling

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODS

Method and Sources of Data

The method used in the process of data collection was majorly browsing through the web and sourcing for data from some important websites such as the CBN Statistical Bulletin, international energy statistics among others.

Model Specification

In this study, the RLS regression model was employed to show the relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth in Nigeria. The model is stated as follows:

$$\log RGDP = \alpha + \beta \log ESS + \gamma \log GCF + \lambda \log TLF + \mu_i \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Where:

RGDP =Gross Domestic Product

ESS =Electricity Supply

GCF =Gross Capital Formation

TLF = Total Labor forces

α = intercept parameter

β, γ and λ = partial slope parameters.

u_i = error term

M Estimator:

One of the robust regression estimation methods is the M estimation. The letter M indicates that M-estimation is an estimation of the maximum likelihood type. If estimator at M-estimation is

$\hat{\beta}_M = \beta_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ then:

$$E[\hat{\beta} = \beta_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)] = \beta \tag{2}$$

This implies that equation (1) is an unbiased estimator with its corresponding variance given as:

$$Var(\hat{\beta}) = \frac{[\tilde{\beta}]^2}{n \cdot E \left[\frac{d}{d\beta} \ln f(x_i; \beta) \right]^2} \tag{3}$$

Where $\tilde{\beta}$ is the linear unbiased estimator for β . M estimation is an extension of the maximum likelihood estimate method and a robust estimation (Yuliana & Susanti, 2008).

Algorithm: M - Estimator

1. Estimate regression coefficients on the data using OLS.
2. Test assumptions of the regression model
3. Detect the presence of outliers in the data.
4. Calculate estimated parameter β_0 with OLS.
5. Calculate residual value $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$
6. Calculate value $\hat{\sigma}_i = 1.4826 MAD$
7. Calculate value $u_i = e_i / \hat{\sigma}_i$
8. Calculate the weighted value using: $w_i = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{u_i}{4.685} \right)^2 \right]^2 & ; |u_i| \leq 4.685 \\ 0 & ; |u_i| > 4.685 \end{cases}$
9. Calculate $\hat{\beta}_M$ using weighted least squares (WLS) method with weighted w_i
10. Repeat steps 5-8 to obtain a convergent value of $\hat{\beta}_M$ and test to determine whether independent variables have significant effect on the dependent variable.

Huber’s weighting function

The function for Huber M estimator is given below.

$$w_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |u_i| \leq c \\ \frac{c}{|u_i|} & \text{if } |u_i| > c \end{cases}$$

Where c is used as **1.542** as the turning constant as suggested by Holland and Welsch (1977) to maintain 95% asymptotic efficiency w.r.t. the LS estimators under normality.

Bisquare weighting function.

The function for Bisquare M estimator is given below.

$$w_i = \begin{cases} (1 - (\frac{u_i}{c})^2)^2 & \text{if } |u_i| \leq c \\ 0 & \text{if } |u_i| > c \end{cases}$$

Where c is used as **4.685** as the turning constant as suggested by Holland and Welsch (1977) to maintain 95% asymptotic efficiency w.r.t. the LS estimators under normality.

Weighting functions have tuning factors, which can be modified. Using tuning factors, it is possible to reduce the impact of outliers with large residuals, but this is achieved at the cost of reducing the estimator efficiency.

MM Estimator: MM estimation provide a high breakdown value and more efficient than M and S estimators. Breakdown value is a common measure of the proportion of outliers that can be addressed before these observations affect the model [3]. MM-estimator is the solution of;

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_1(u_i) X_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_1 \left(\frac{Y_i - \sum_{j=0}^k X_{ij} \beta_j}{S_{MM}} \right) X_{ij} = 0 \tag{4}$$

Where S_{MM} is the standard deviation of S estimation and ρ is the Turkey’s biweight function defined by:

$$\rho(u_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{u_i^2}{2} - \frac{u_i^4}{2c^2} + \frac{u_i^6}{6c^2}, & -c \leq u_i \leq c \\ \frac{c^2}{6}, & u_i < -c \text{ or } u_i > c \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Algorithm: MM Estimator

1. Estimate regression coefficients on the data using OLS.
2. Test assumptions of the regression model

3. Detect the presence of outliers in the data.
4. Calculate residual value $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$ of S estimate
5. Calculate $\hat{\sigma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{sn}$
6. Calculate $u_i = \frac{e_i}{\hat{\sigma}_i}$
7. Calculate the weighted value w_i :

$$w_i = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{u_i}{4.685}\right)^2\right]^2, & |u_i| \leq 4.685 \\ 0, & |u_i| > 4.685 \end{cases}$$

8. Calculate $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$ using weighted least square method with weighted w_i
9. Repeat step 5 – 8 to obtain a convergent value of $\hat{\beta}_{MM}$ and test whether the independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Measure of Performance and selection criteria for best model

The best estimator will be selected based on remedying outlier and high leverage point problem better than the others. The performance of the estimators will be evaluated by residual standard error (RSE) of the model. The method with smaller RSE is regarded as the best method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unit Root Test Result

As part of the requirements of time series data, unit root test using augmented dickey fuller test was employed to test for the stationarity properties of the data for the study. The unit root test result is presented thus:

Table 1: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test Results

Variables	I(ORDER)	ADF	P value
LGDP	I (1)	-5.393644	0.0006***
LESS	I (1)	-5.593450	0.0005***
LGCF	I (1)	-6.919300	0.0000***
LTLF	I (1)	-3.082067	0.0351**

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.1.1. *** (**) indicates significance at 1% & 5% levels respectively. GDP represents Real Gross domestic product, ESS represents electricity supply, GCF represents Gross Capital formation and TLF represents Total labor forces respectively.

The above result reveals the stationarity of the variables used, in which case, both series log(RGDP), log(ESS), log(GCF), and log(TLF) were simultaneously stationary at first difference with I (1) order of integration as depicted above.

Table 2: Bisquare M Estimation Result for default tuning constant value and adjusted C=4.685, 3.685 and 5.685 respectively.

Variables	Coefficient	S.E	t-value	p-value
Constant	25.5117	0.5020	50.8231	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.0026	0.0081	-0.3241	0.3003
GCF	-0.2407	0.1940	-1.2405	1.076e-10***
TLF	0.0056	0.0031	1.7926	0.1282
RSE 0.3866				
Constant	25.1384	0.2321	108.2939	2e-15 ***
ESS	0.0008	0.0038	0.2107	0.3003
GCF	-0.1849	0.0897	-2.0610	1.076e-10***
TLF	0.0066	0.0015	4.5660	0.101
RSE 0.2005				
Constant	25.4645	0.4955	51.3911	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.0030	0.0080	-0.3691	0.3450
GCF	-0.2016	0.1915	-1.0525	1.076e-10***
TLF	0.0053	0.0031	1.7116	0.6510
RSE 0.4062				

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.1.1. *** (**) indicates significance at 1% & 5% levels respectively.

Table 3: Huber M Estimation Result for default tuning constant value and adjusted

K= 1.547, 1 and 2.547					
Variables		Coefficient	S.E	t-value	p-value
Constant		25.6653	0.4673	54.92352e-15 ***	
ESS		-0.0035	0.0076	-0.4598	0.3560
GCF		-0.2889	0.1806	-1.5993	1.076e-10***
TLF		0.0056	0.0029	1.9077	0.1982
	RSE	0.401			
Constant		25.6097	0.4454	57.50052e-15 ***	
ESS		-0.0027	0.0072	-0.3786	0.3053
GCF		-0.2898	0.1722	-1.6835	1.076e-10***
TLF		0.0059	0.0028	2.1007	0.101
	RSE	0.3673			
Constant		25.7200	0.5377	47.8298 2e-15 ***	
ESS		-0.0046	0.0087	-0.5294	0.3550
GCF		-0.2733	0.2079	-1.3146	1.076e-10***
TLF		0.0051	0.0034	1.5140	0.6810
	RSE	0.4953			

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.1.1. *** (**) indicates significance at 1% & 5% levels respectively.

Table 4: Bisquare MM Estimation Result for default tuning constant value and adjusted C=4.685, 3.685 and 5.685 respectively.

Variables	Coefficient	S.E	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.1809	0.1333	1.3571	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.7061	0.0022	-326.8709	0.0968
GCF	0.2476	0.0515	4.8037	1.91e-13 ***
TLF	1.6921	0.0008	2029.2663	0.0446 *
RSE	0.1507			
Constant	0.0959	0.1258	0.7623	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.7177	0.0020	-352.1635	0.0958
GCF	0.2517	0.0486	5.1772	1.89e-13 ***
TLF	1.7010	0.0008	2162.4091	0.0449 *
RSE	0.1507			
Constant	-4.1900	0.2173	-19.2795	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.0523	0.0035	-14.8467	0.0918
GCF	0.4200	0.0840	4.9994	1.91e-13 ***
TLF	1.6478	0.0014	1212.3480	0.0449 *
RSE	0.1507			

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.1.1. *** (***) indicates significance at 1% & 5% levels respectively.

Table 5: Huber MM Estimation Result for default tuning constant value and adjusted.

K= 1.547, 1 and 2.547				
Variables	Coefficient	S.E	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.1810	0.1333	1.3572	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.7061	0.0022	-326.8737	0.0968
GCF	0.2476	0.0515	4.8037	1.91e-13 ***
TLF	1.6921	0.0008	2029.2771	1.91e-13 ***
RSE	0.1507			
Constant	0.1809	0.1333	1.3571	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.7061	0.0022	-326.8718	0.0958
GCF	0.2476	0.0515	4.8037	1.89e-13 ***
TLF	1.6921	0.0008	2029.2698	0.0459 *
RSE	0.1507			
Constant	0.1810	0.1333	1.3573	2e-15 ***
ESS	-0.7061	0.0022	-326.8755	0.0818
GCF	0.2476	0.0515	4.8037	1.91e-13 ***
TLF	1.6921	0.0008	2029.2842	0.0469 *
RSE	0.1507			

Source: Authors' computation aided by R package v 4.1.1. *** (**) indicates significance at 1% & 5% levels respectively.

Table 6: Comparing the Performances of the default and adjusted tuning constant values of M and MM robust estimators based on Huber and Bisquare weighting functions.

Methods	Bisquare		Huber	
	RSE		RSE	
Tuning constant(C,K)	M	MM	M	MM
Default	0.3866	0.1507	0.401	0.1507
Decreased	0.2005	0.1507	0.3673	0.1507
Increased	0.4062	0.1507	0.4953	0.1507

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 2 to 5 showed the result of M and MM robust estimators regression result based on Huber and Bisquare weights using the default and decreased/increased tuning constant values on determining the effects of electricity consumption on economic growth of Nigeria. Table 6 compared the performance of the two robust methods based on Huber and Bisquare functions using the default and adjusted tuning constant values respectively. It can be seen from table 6 above, that as we decrease the default value from (4.685) to (3.685) the Residual standard error (RSE) also decreases from (0.2005) to (0.3866) meaning that, the resistibility of the M-estimator increases by reducing the default value. we have also noticed that by increasing the default value to (5.685) the RSE also increases from (0.3866) to (0.4062), meaning that

the resistibility of the estimator against outliers' decreases. Likewise, if we look at the result of M-estimation using Huber weight in Table 3 above the situation is same as that of Bisquare, but the bisquare perform better than the Huber having the lowest residuals in all the three situations. While looking at the result of MM-estimator for both Bisquare and Huber in Table 4 and 5, we have noticed that the result found to be the same (0.1507) across all the situations examined. Meaning that adjusting the tuning constant value on MM estimator has no any impact on the resistibility of the model. On the other hand, the used of MM-estimator reveals that the overall fit of the model improves and the significance of the predictors changes significantly compared to M-estimation methods. Finally, the result of the regression predictors showed that over time higher electricity consumption give rise to more economic growth, just as economic growth may stimulate increased consumption of electricity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, we can say that adjusting the tuning constant values for M estimator both for Bisquare and Huber have a significant impact on the resistibility of the estimators against outlying observations. From the result of the study, we can conclude that decreasing the default tuning constant value of M-estimation for Huber and Bisquare from (4.685) to (3.685) and from (1.547) to (1) would increase the resistibility of the estimators against outlying observations in the regression model. While, for MM-estimator decreasing/increasing the turning constant has no any impact on the resistibility of the model. Therefore, the study recommended that analyst should use smaller value than the default tuning constant for M-estimation to have more resistibility against outlying observations. Likewise, researchers should adopt the use of Bisquare for data with large outliers rather than Huber. Finally, the study recommends that government should formulate appropriate policy mix that would motivate the firms in the electricity industry to enhance improved performance and contribution of the sector.

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